

Green Motivation, Environmentally Friendly Intellectuals, and Green Innovation Toward Green Competitive Advantage at PT Kalbe Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The environment functions as a resource for the survival and sustainability of industrial activities themselves as well as a place to live or stand. Companies such as PT Kalbe Indonesia, as well as the community and government, are paying attention and taking serious action on these environmental issues. Regarding the state of the environment and depletion of natural resources, the company has made a significant contribution. which got worse. Businesses should encourage green production in their operations, but a green environment does not necessarily require zero pollution. This research aims to examine the behavior of environmentally friendly employees towards green innovation. To achieve green competitive advantage (Y) and green innovation (Z), manufacturing companies need green intelligence (X2) and green motivation (X1) in their operations. This research method is a literature review that compares several existing theories with previous research. The output of this research was submitted to an international journal, namely Copernicus

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is the most interesting thing for local and international tourists to visit (Ansari et al., 2021). Two years earlier, the impact of Covid 19 caused the tourism industry to stop functioning; However, after the COVID-19 period ended, tourism emerged as a major attraction. (Aluko et al., 2021). Each region has a different attraction in terms of tourism, the environment is not only a place to live but also a resource for the continuity and continuity of industrial activities themselves (Amoako, 2020). However, without realizing it, the environment is being damaged by the company's activities (Asiaei et al., 2022). Company waste and activities have a negative impact and cause damage to the environment (Astuti & Wahyuni, 2018). Water, land, and air pollution, landfilling of waste that exceeds capacity, global warming, ecosystem damage, the emergence of various diseases, floods, and other natural disasters are examples of damage that has been done to the environment. The worst example is the Earth which is on the verge of destruction (Anwar et al., 2020).

The environmental issues above are a very serious problem, the community and government are also paying serious attention and taking action towards this matter (Asadi et al., 2020). Companies have a big contribution to make regarding the increasingly deteriorating natural environment. A green environment does not always have to be zero pollution, industry must encourage green production in its activities (Benevene & Buonomo, 2020).

Several studies reveal factors that can influence either directly or indirectly corporate green competitive advantage, namely: researching employee eco-friendly behavior in green human resources management which supports green environmental performance and competitive advantage of a company or organization (Chaudhary, 2020).

Meanwhile, research examining the Green Intellectual Capital factor in research on Green Intellectual Capital is linked to green motivation, green innovation, and green environmental performance which will later create a tourism situation that has good competitiveness (A'yuni & Muafi, 2020).

There has been no previous research regarding the relationship between Corporate Green Competitive Advantage mediated by Green Environmental Performance and controlled by the Green Commitment variable (Batool et al., 2019). Looking at the various results of previous research, it is necessary to retest to see whether the results will be consistent or if there are changes, especially if empirical updates are carried out on these variables (Farheen et al., 2020). The updates that researchers carry out here are updates to empirical evidence and building models that combine previous theories (Fang et al., 202

LITERATURE REVIEW

Author and Year

Alam & Islam (2021)

Definitions

Greiein Competitivei Advantagei has been described as a condition of innovation that cannot be imitated by others where the company takes a position over ecological management or sustainable innovation.

Widiyati & Muirwaningsari
(2021)

Greiein Competitivei Advantagei Greiein Competitivei Advantagei is a situation where a company reaches an advantage compared to competitors' companies in market competition.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of writing this article is to review and summarize the literature review related to the implementation of employee engagement in multinational companies so that they know what factors can be effectively used to increase employee engagement through various methods, other career factors, and transactions. management, Recruitment, and Organizational Commitment, researchers attempt to read, analyze, and summarize literature reviews from various journals and other related information sources to determine a strategy to implement effective employee engagement in an organization. This study uses a literature review approach to achieve the research objectives. The mini-assessment of employee engagement is conducted by reading and analyzing several peer-reviewed journal articles. This research method is a literature review that compares several existing theories and previous studies. To obtain the information and data necessary for this work, the following data collection methods are used: Documents/Library, ie. a data collection technique for researching documents related to the researched problem. The data analysis method of this study uses the literature review analysis method using an inductive reasoning model. The analysis process is carried out using a data analysis technique, which is content analysis. In other words, a detailed description of data and context, their nature, characteristics, content, reasoning, and the use of inductive logic to draw conclusions.

RESULTS

Employee environmentally friendly behavior is referred to as Environmental Overall Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCBE) and is a voluntary individual action that leads to effective environmental performance in an organization (Purnama et al., 2021).

Indonesian people are increasingly environmentally conscious (Febrian & Purnama, 2022). Based on the 2022 Green Industry Report, research shows that as many as 55% of consumers in 60 countries are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2021). At least 71% of Americans, according to one study, think about the environment when they shop. From current green business practices, green functional areas such as green HR management have developed (Majid et al., 2022).

Competitiveness is one of the most important advantages for an organization. Every company must try to create a new competitive environment or dimension, if necessary, always competing to determine new rules of the game. To be able to survive in a more competitive environment, companies need to implement strategies, which were previously formulated through external and internal analysis (Gupta & Gupta, 2020).

Competitive strategy is the search for a profitable competitive position in an industry, because of the fundamentals in which competition occurs (Hadjri et al., 2020).

Companies must have innovative products so that profits increase and have an advantage in competition. Currently innovation in companies is a necessity, and many innovations are related to things that are environmentally friendly (Widiyati & Murwaningsari, 2021). It is believed that a company's competitiveness is positively influenced by the components of environmental product innovation and environmental process innovation (Hang et al., 2022).

DISCUSSION

Green motivation is something that is important for an employee in a company to achieve a green competitive advantage in the PT Kalbe Indonesia Company. Environmentally friendly intellectuals are of course also very necessary to gain a green competitive advantage, this will of course have a very positive influence on achieving a green competitive advantage. Likewise, green innovation will really support the achievement of the vision and mission aimed at by a company, especially for achieving green competitive advantage at PT Kalbe Indonesia

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research suggests that companies can improve all the variables in this research in order to increase their green competitive advantage

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Green Motivation, Environmentally Friendly Intellectuals, and Green Innovation Toward Green Competitive Advantage in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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